

Study of Non-Gaseous Products formed in γ -Radiolysis of Benzene*

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It has been shown that the injection port-temperature of the vapour phase chromatograph influences considerably the analytical result obtained for biphenyl. This has been attributed to pyrolysis of some polymers formed in γ -radiolysis of benzene. G (biphenyl) measured below 200°C has a value of 0.063. Doses in the range of 1 Mrad-40 Mrads do not alter the pyrolytic behaviour of the polymers. In the case of radiolysis of additive solutions of benzene, G (biphenyl) values of 0.082, 0.1 and 0.12 are obtained for 2.8×10^{-3} M iodine, 10% chloroform and 10% carbon tetrachloride solution respectively. No injection port-temperature effect is observed in these solutions. These results appear to be consistent with the view that polymer responsible for this behaviour could be a hydrogenated biphenyl.

The radiolysis of liquid benzene has been extensively studied in the pure state as well as in multicomponent systems¹⁻⁹ and as such, a great deal is known about the gaseous products. However, non-gaseous products which are formed with much higher yield, (G polymer = 0.75)⁸ have so far not even been fully characterised. Gordon *et al.*¹⁰ fractionally distilled the products and found C_{12} , C_{18} and C_{18} components to be 18.6%, 57.6% and 23.6% respectively, whereas Gaumann³ identified a large number of products (though bulk still remains unidentified) by vapour phase chromatography. During the course of our studies¹¹, it was observed that one or more products on pyrolysis yield biphenyl. Since pyrolytic studies offer an additional technique for investigating polymeric products, we extended the earlier work with the hope that the results would be helpful in characterising and estimating some polymers formed in γ -radiolysis of benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

G. R. grade benzene (E. Merck) was triple crystallised rejecting one-fourth each time. All other chemicals used were of the highest quality commercially available. A known

1. Gaumann and Schuler, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 709.
2. Patrick and Burton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2626.
3. Burton and Gordon, *Disc. Faraday. Soc.*, 1952, **12**, 88.
4. Manion and Burton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 360.
5. Gaumann *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1961, **44**, 1357 and 1963, **46**, 2873.
6. Schuler, *Trans. Faraday. Soc.*, 1965, **61**, 100.
7. Burns, *ibid.*, 1962, **58**, 961.
8. Chermiak, Collinson and Dainton, *ibid.*, 1964, **60**, 1408.
9. VanDusen and Hamill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 3648.
10. Gordon, Van Dyken and Doumani, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 20.
11. Srivastava, *Radio Chem. Acta.*, 1966, **5**(1), 53.

Also see reference No. 6 in Peterson, Arakawa Walmsley and Burton, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 2880.

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amount of the liquid in a pyrex capsule, was degassed on a vacuum line by repeated freeze and thaw technique. Irradiation of such samples were carried out in a 23 kilocurie Co-60 source having a dose rate $\approx 2 \times 10^{18}$ ev/g/min. Administered dose was measured by using Curie-Cerous dosimeter using $G(\text{Cu}^{2+}) = 2.44^{12}$.

Non-gaseous products were analysed on a high temperature vapour phase chromatograph designed and fabricated in the laboratory¹³. A flame ionisation assembly was used as detector. The injection port block was made of stainless steel and had a volume ≈ 0.1 ml. Apiezon L (10% by weight) on chromosorb-W was used as a column material. An 8 ft. long column made of $\frac{1}{8}$ " (O.D.) copper tube, coiled in the required shape, was operated at 175°C. Since the instrument was not sensitive to concentrations lower than 5×10^{-3} M, all estimations were made in the range of 5×10^{-3} M— 5×10^{-2} M by distilling off some solvent from the irradiated solutions. A blank run when similarly made showed absence of appreciable loss of product measured by this process of concentration. The analytical results for biphenyl are accurate to within $10 \pm \%$.

Biphenyl was the only product measured. $G(\text{biphenyl})$ thus obtained from pure benzene was 0.083 ± 0.007 which is in excellent agreement with Gaumann's⁶ result. On varying the injection port temperature, which could be controlled manually by means of a variac, $G(\text{biphenyl})$ obtained on this instrument, was found to increase with the injection port-temperature. This is consistent with the observations made earlier by Srivastava¹¹ on F.M. Model 609 gas chromatograph. A blank sample of unirradiated benzene under these conditions (also when heated outside in a furnace at 300°C for 10 minutes) did not produce any biphenyl.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows $G(\text{biphenyl})$ as a function of injection port-temperature. It also shows the effect of dose (1 Mrad–10 Mrad) on the pyrolytic behaviour of the polymer formed. It would be seen that in all cases $G(\text{biphenyl})$ remains constant up to injection port temperature of $\approx 200^\circ\text{C}$. Pyrolysis of polymeric products becomes appreciable only at higher temperatures when an increase in biphenyl yield is observed. It would be also seen that the observed γ -dose does not affect the magnitude of pyrolysis indicating that the yield of polymeric product responsible for increase in biphenyl yield is independent of dose.

Fig. 2 shows the effect of additives (I_2 , CHCl_3 and CCl_4) on G initial (biphenyl)* and on the pyrolytic behaviour of polymeric product responsible for additional yield of biphenyl. It is seen that G initial (biphenyl) goes up in all cases and remains invariant with change in injection port-temperature. This indicates absence of such polymeric products as are responsible for increase in biphenyl yield. Also, in the case of iodine solution of benzene, $G(\text{biphenyl})$ appeared to depend on dose inasmuch as a value of 0.083 and 0.25 was obtained for G initial (biphenyl) for doses of 1 Mrad and 5 Mrad respectively. Nevertheless, no difference in the subsequent thermal behaviour was observed.

12. Boyle, *Radiation Research*, 1962, 17, 427.

13. K. Narayana Rao, *et al.*, AFET/CD/8.

* $G(\text{biphenyl})$ measured at the lowest injection port-temperature below 200°C .

FIG.1. DOSE EFFECTS

FIG.2. EFFECT OF ADDITIVES.

DISCUSSION

The three interesting points emerging from these studies are :

- (a) dependence of G (biphenyl) on injection port-temperature,
- (b) absence of dose effect on G (biphenyl), and

- (c) increase in G initial (biphenyl) and its independence on injection port-temperatures when iodine, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride are used as additives.

Radiolysis of benzene results in formation of a large number of products of which polymeric compounds constitute a major fraction. The complexity of the latter has been reported to be strongly dependent on integrated γ -dose and in fact Patrick and Burton⁸ have demonstrated that in the dose range $\sim 2 \times 10^{22}$ ev/ml to $\sim 7 \times 10^{22}$ ev/ml, the average molecular weight of the polymers varies from 225 to 430. As such when this relationship is extrapolated to the current range of dose employed, viz., 5.7×10^{19} ev/ml to 2.28×10^{20} ev/ml, a corresponding number in the neighbourhood of 160 is obtained for molecular weight of the polymers formed. Since the molecular weights of dimer and trimer are 154 and 230 respectively, it is reasonable to assume that the increase in biphenyl yield in radiolysed pure benzene at elevated injection port-temperatures is due to pyrolytic behaviour of certain hydrogenated C_{12} products. Some of the dimers produced in this dose range have been identified to be phenyl hexatriene⁵ ($G=0.02$), phenyl cyclohexadiene—2,4 ($G=0.029$), phenyl cyclohexadiene—2,5 ($G=0.041$) and biphenyl ($G=0.063$). Phenylcyclohexadienes have been found to be thermally stable under these conditions. The rest (exclusive of biphenyl) even if quantitatively pyrolysed to produce biphenyl can give only an additional G (biphenyl) = 0.025 as compared to 0.657 increase observed in the present studies. Recently Charniak *et al.*¹³ have further identified some more products bringing the total assignment of polymers to $\sim 50\%$. According to these workers, 3 phenylcyclohex-1-ene is the most important dimer formed ($G=0.22$) but it is not known whether this could yield biphenyl on pyrolysis. Hückel and Schwen¹⁶ believe that 1-phenylcyclohex-1,4 diene is unstable and can yield biphenyl but this compound has so far not been detected in irradiated benzene. Also G total polymers (terphenyl and polyphenyl) reported is 0.0484 but they are not known to decompose at the injection port temperatures employed here. Obviously some hitherto undetected products are responsible for injection port-temperature effect. This aspect needs further investigation.

Radiolysis of iodine solution of benzene is very complex and is not fully understood as yet. Depending on relative concentrations, halogen species could scavenge phenyl radicals or react with their precursors to give phenyl halide¹⁴. This could result in diminished yield of pyrolysable products in such solutions and explain absence of injection port-temperature effect. Charniak *et al.*¹³ did observe diminished yield of certain dimers (not accountable for absence of injection port-temperature but indicative of the fact that yield of other dimers also could be similarly affected) in the radiolysis of ferric chloride solution of benzene. Halogens are also capable of dehydrogenating phenylcyclohexadienes to yield additional biphenyl. This can account for higher G initial (biphenyl) shown in Fig. 2 for solutions containing additives. Dependence of G initial (biphenyl) on dose in such solutions, on the other hand, is difficult to explain though Fellows and Schuler¹⁴ have observed that in such systems iodine consumption increases exponentially with dose. Halogen species

14. Fellows and Schuler *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 1451.

15. Charniak, Oullinson and Danton, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, 60, 1408.

16. Hückel and Schwen, *Ber.*, 1956, 89, 150.

could also destroy unsaturation produced in this system but it is not known whether such compounds would be thermally more stable than the corresponding parent compound to rationalise the present result. Further work for elucidation of these is in progress and the result would be communicated elsewhere.

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